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SUBSTANTIATION OF THE CONCEPTUAL BASIS AND STRUCTURE OF STATE SECURITY AS AN OBJECT OF PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION

The object of research is state security and its element-by-element structure in the context of the objective attention of public administration. A problematic aspect is the lack of clarity of interpretation of the main category and identification of components of state security, which slows down the formation of effective mechanisms of public administration in the field of state security, and thus reduces its effectiveness.

The study used methods of analysis and synthesis, induction and deduction, as well as decomposition, which allowed to clarify the definition of state security, its structure and provide a primary description of these components.

The definition of «state security» is formed. It is proposed to understand the state of protection of various vector interests of the state and the citizen, which ensures the effective functioning of all spheres, industries, institutional sectors, mechanisms, implementation of functions and powers of the state for their development. An important emphasis on this situation is its achievement in a changing environment, external and internal threats. The separation of the following types of components of state security with the corresponding content load is motivated: security of national administration; political security; economic security; military security; security of public and legal order; social and humanitarian security; information and communication security; resource and environmental security; technical and technogenic safety; international diplomatic security.

In comparison with the existing approaches, the applied unification terminological approach allows to emphasize quite concretely the content of concepts in the context of their «historical nature». In contrast to the existing approaches to the structure of state security, the presented segmentation of state security takes into account the domestic regulatory framework, global approaches to determining the objective attention of the state and its threats, current trends in civil society. Due to the implementation of the author's proposals in practice, state security as an object of public administration acquires a clear systematics, which allows to form both scientifically sound mechanisms of the latter and new areas of research.

Keywords: *effective mechanisms of public administration, unification terminological approach, state security structure, development of civil society.*

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1. Introduction

Traditionally, one of the central objects of government in any country is state security. However, despite the stability of the latter phenomenon, its components, and therefore priorities, are constantly changing. This trend has been most clearly manifested in recent decades against the background of a deep acceleration of global, regional and local changes of a diverse nature. So, at the present time all over the world there are acute issues of cybernetic, epidemiological, biological, economic, man-made, military security, requiring an urgent solution through the consolidation of the efforts of all mankind. The latter is possible only under conditions of strengthening direct leadership by the state, which, in

turn (as demonstrated by the world events of recent years), obviously needs modernization on scientifically grounded principles.

So, in these conditions, the study of issues of state security in general and its components in particular in the context of object attention of public administration becomes relevant.

2. The object of research and its technological audit

The object of the research is state security and its element-by-element structure in the context of object attention of public administration. State security is an objective

condition for the functioning of any country. Modern studies of the developed world indicate that approaches to the identification of the concept of «state security» and the components of the latter have long been developed. The authors of the latest publications focus their attention on the most critical positions to which they refer: extremism and radicalism, cybersecurity, social security, communication security, etc. [1]. Let's consider state security on the example of Ukraine, in which, despite the established traditions, it requires revision and modernization. At the same time, not only from the standpoint of the existing elements of the latter, but also taking into account the changing environment, globalization processes, the development of post-industrial society and other defining trends of our time.

The most problematic moments are the approaches to their own definition of the concept of «state security» and the identification of its components. Despite the rather active study of these issues by the scientific community, they have not received a specific conceptualization; at the same time, the presence of their clear systematization is decisive for any further research in this area.

3. The aim and objectives of research

The aim of research is to study the conceptual basis and structure of «state security» in the context of object attention of public administration.

To achieve the set aim of research, the following objectives have been identified:

1. Analyze approaches to the interpretation of the concept of «state security» and form the author's definition of software for the development of its substantive components.
2. Determine the components of state security and provide them with an initial description.

4. Research of existing solutions to the problem

The work [2] confirms the authors' point of view on the colossal number of options for interpreting the concepts of «state/national security» and notes the ideological commitment of many authors of scientific research in this direction. Also, attention is focused on many attempts to distribute national, state and global security, which have not received a positive result. In addition, the work noted on the most relevant objects of state/national security of the modern world, such as: economy, food, health, ecology, politics, personality and society in the focus of law enforcement, ethnic and religious issues. However, the issue of defining the concept of «state security» and its structured nature is not considered.

The author of [3] supports the point of view that «state/national security» is the preservation of norms, rules, institutions and values of society, providing a clear targeting interpretation.

In [4], state/national security is considered in the context of information security and the need to interpret it according to the degree of secrecy of information and access of officials to such information, and the principles of the latter, are noted. However, the issue of other components is not dealt with in the publication.

The author of the publication [5] proves the need to take into account the «right to information» of citizens

when defining the concepts of state/national security, which includes confidentiality, freedom of speech, access, and the like. Despite the importance of the aspect raised, the author does not identify the very concept of «state security».

In [6] it is emphasized that everything that threatens the physical well-being of the population or threatens the stability of the economy or institutions of the country should be considered national security. At the same time, such objects of attention were highlighted: terrorism, hostile governments, the spread of aggressiveness of the latter, cyber terrorism, epidemics and natural disasters. Despite the presented elemental structure of national security, the conceptual apparatus is not systematized and detailed in this work.

The author of the subsequent publication [7] examines national security in the context of scientific and technical activities and products, noting the problems of the limits of access to the latter of society and the concealment of classified information. Despite the importance of the issue raised, the study does not cover the content of the concept of «national security».

The author of [8] understands national/state security as the ability of the armed forces and law enforcement agencies to protect the sovereignty of the nation and the lives of its people. And also, using internal and external military tools, to protect the nation from terrorist and other attacks both inside the country and abroad. Obviously, the author focuses exclusively on the military and law enforcement functions of the state in the context of national security, avoiding considering others.

A review of well-known world-class national security periodicals testifies to the elaboration of such topics by the authors of these publications in the context of national security:

- [9] – climate change, domestic terrorism, radicalism, cybersecurity, nuclear weapons, piracy, space, refugees;
- [10] – social networks, epidemic, human rights, domestic terrorism and extremism;
- [11] – weapons, extremism, energy resources, corruption, domestic terrorism.

An appeal to Ukrainian authors made it possible to single out clearer approaches to this problematic definition to confirm this statement [12, 13]. However, despite their acquisition of a clear formulation of the concept of «state security» and systematization of the components of state security did not happen, which complicates the formation of methodological approaches to the actual definition, assessment and control of the latter.

5. Methods of research

In the process of performing the work, general scientific and special research methods were applied:

- analysis and synthesis – for a preliminary analysis of approaches to the formation of the concept of «state security», as well as the components of state security;
- deduction and induction – for the formation of the concept of «state security», as well as the characteristics of the components of state security;
- method of decompositions – when forming the composition of state security.

6. Research results

The current stage of development of the civilizational world is characterized by: the acceleration of globalization

processes, the rapid development of information technologies, the multidimensionality and variability of not only public life, but also crisis phenomena. All this is happening against the backdrop of the presence of many different factors of uncertainty, threats and risks. In these conditions, the formation of mechanisms in the field of state security is the key to sustainable development not only of an individual state, but also of any institutional unit. The concept of state security is complex and multifaceted. Let's consider its actual characteristics and components.

First of all, let's turn to Ukrainian legislation, within the framework of which the Law of Ukraine «On the National Security of Ukraine» [14] offers the concept of both national and state security. «National security of Ukraine – protection of state sovereignty, territorial integrity, democratic constitutional order and other national interests of Ukraine from real and potential threats; state security – the protection of state sovereignty, territorial integrity and democratic constitutional order and other vital national interests from real and potential threats of a non-military nature» [14]. Let's note that the difference between these concepts actually lies in the emphasis on state security on non-military threats. It is also worth noting that the only mention of state security in Article 1 «Definition of terms» of the above Law and complete disregard of this concept in the main text of the latter is seen as insufficiently clear.

Encyclopedic publications suggest that state security be understood as «a set of conditions and institutions that are designed to guarantee the sovereignty of the state, the protection of its territory, population, state institutions and external threats. State security is also understood as a state of balance between the military and socio-economic potential of a country and a complex of threats that can lead to conflict. In the system of state security, external and internal components are distinguished ... state security includes issues of environmental, energy, information, social security, etc.» [15].

Processing more than 10 publications over the last 20-year period, representing the point of view of different authors regarding the concept of «state security», made it possible to carry out the following generalization of their approaches (Fig. 1).

The processing of the philosophical understanding of the concept of «security» and the presented approaches to

the interpretation of the concept of «state security» made it possible to form the author's definition of this concept. It is proposed to understand the state of protection of different-vector interests of the state and the citizen, in which the effective functioning of all spheres, industries, institutional sectors, mechanisms, the implementation of the functions and powers of the state with the aim of their development is ensured. An important emphasis on this state is seen in its achievement in a changing environment, external and internal threats. The unification approach proposed in a certain way allows a rather specific emphasis on the content of the concept as a logically connected set of corresponding objects, in the context of the prevailing philosophical nature of the phenomenon of «security». At the same time, the «volume» of the concept itself remained open for further more thorough detailing of its characteristics in the segment of the theoretical foundations of the science of public administration in the field of state security in terms of its elemental components.

It should be noted that despite the extensive discussion of the characteristics of the concept of «state security», the issue of the components of the latter was worked out very limitedly. The current Law of Ukraine «On the National Security of Ukraine» avoids such a division, appealing within the limits of national security in military security, public security and order, state security [14]. At the same time, the current National Security Strategy of Ukraine [16] presupposes the adoption of such subcontracting documents within the latter. «Strategies for human development, Strategies for military security of Ukraine, Strategies for public security and civil protection of Ukraine, Strategies for the development of the military-industrial complex of Ukraine, Strategies for economic security, Strategy for energy security, Strategies for environmental safety and adaptation to climate change, Strategies for biosafety and biological protection, Strategies information security, the Cybersecurity Strategy of Ukraine, the Foreign Policy Strategy of the State Security Strategy, the Integrated Border Management Strategy, the Food Security Strategy and the National Intelligence Program» [16]. In fact, the list of the above normative documents confirms the status of the security areas enshrined in the latest directions as components of national security as a whole.

Fig. 1. Multi-vector interpretations of the concept of «state security» (developed by the authors on the basis of data [12, 13, 15–26])

With regard to such existing misunderstandings and discrepancies in regulatory documents, it is extremely appropriate and timely to study, in which the author of the work substantiated, reasoned, logically and consistently proves the need to appeal first of all to the term «state security», and only then to national security [12].

In general, scientists note the integrality of the concept of state security, which should completely include the sphere of functioning of the state and society. Views on such areas differ in a certain way, in particular, various authors include the following components in the composition of state security:

- economic security, information security, the fight against separatism, counteraction to the political radicalization of society [13];
- internal and external state security [17];
- ecological, energy, informational, social, humanitarian spheres [18];
- political, economic, military, environmental, informational, social, demographic, food, radiation safety [19];
- fight against terrorism, economic information and cyber security [20].

Obviously, when forming the components of state security, scientists etymologically relied on the vocabulary unit «state». The meaning of the latter is most fully presented in the following context. «The state is a political form of organization of government, characterized by sovereign power, political and public nature, the exercise of its powers in a certain territory through a system of specially created bodies and organizations, with the help of which political, economic and ideological management of society and the management of public rights are carried out» [21].

In fact, protection, and hence the security of escort, requires each of the specific functional directions of the state's actions, which primarily include [21]: economic, political, social, humanitarian; economic, political, social, environmental, informational, humanitarian, law enforcement.

Also, the writings talk about the diplomatic direction, international cooperation, environmental protection, protection of the territory of the state, protection of human rights and freedoms, cultural, defensive, debt, customs, ensuring peace, communicative, normal functioning of the civil society.

An appeal to the Constitution of Ukraine revealed the following set of obligations of the state to implement security [27]:

- sovereignty (Art. 2);
- personality (Art. 3, 27–29);
- state power, constitution (Art. 5);
- local self-government (Art. 7);
- citizenship (Art. 25);
- property rights (Art. 13);
- views and beliefs (Art. 34);
- health protection (art. 49);
- education (Art. 53);
- creativity (Art. 54).

Also, the Constitution [27] says about security:

- environmental, radiation (Art. 16);
- informational, military, territorial (Art. 3, 17);
- social (Art. 3, 17, 44, 46, 47);
- foreign policy (Art.18);
- constitutional (art. 24);
- public (Art. 39);
- labor (Art. 44);

- national, customs, budget, tax, monetary, foreign exchange (Art. 92);
- legal and legal (Art. 59–61);
- ethnic, linguistic, cultural, religious (Art. 10, 11);
- natural resource (Art. 14);
- political, economic, ideological (Art. 15, 17, 34, 36, 44).

The functional approach of the UN and the International Monetary Fund, set out in the Manual on Government Finance Statistics, is seen as interesting and relevant to study. According to this document, the functional directions of the state are as follows: general management, defense, public order and security, economic direction, environmental protection, housing and communal services, health care, recreation, culture and religion, education, social protection [22, 23, 28].

On the basis of a critical analysis of approaches to the components of state security, taking into account the development trends of modern society, such a combination of components of state security with the corresponding content is proposed (Table 1).

Table 1

Characteristics of the components of state security

Component name	Definition of the concept
General management security	The state of protection of the general public administration system from diversified threats in order to ensure its functioning and further development
Political security	The state of protection of the political system of the state from various threats in order to ensure its functioning and further development
Economic security	The state of protection of the state economy from multifactorial threats in the context of ensuring the development of all its institutional sectors
Military security	The state of protection of state sovereignty, territorial integrity and democratic constitutional order and other vital state interests from military threats
Public and legal security	The state of protection of the interests, rights and freedoms of man and citizen, vital for society and the individual, against threats to their peace and property rights, as well as the activities of economic entities
Social and humanitarian security	The state of protection of the social, educational, scientific, cultural, spiritual, medical, media spheres from multi-vector threats to ensure their functioning and further development
Information and communication security	The state of protection of methods, processes and ways of using computers and communication systems from threats of theft, change and destruction of information in order to ensure the effective organization of human activities
Resource and environmental safety	The state of protection of the environment and the subsoil of the state from threats of imbalance, destruction, ineffective use in order to ensure their preservation and restoration
International diplomatic security	The state of protection of the international and diplomatic sphere of the state from external threats to the state in order to ensure peace and good-neighborly partnerships

This segmentation of state security takes into account the domestic legal framework, world approaches to determining the object's attention of the state and its threats, current trends in the development of civil society.

7. SWOT analysis of research results

Strengths. Strengths lie in the clarity and objectivity of the provided definition of «state security», which conceptually focuses on the most significant positions: subjects, objects, conditions of functioning. As well as the consistency of the proposed classification and definitions of the proposed structural elements of state security, taking into account the domestic legal framework, world approaches to the definition of state security and its threats, modern trends in the development of civil society.

Weaknesses. State security specialists traditionally focus exclusively on military security and security in the context of law enforcement, and this emphasis is logical both in the definition and in the approaches to classification. So, despite a scientifically based approach and a modern world vision of the content, role and goals of state security, Ukrainian state security specialists may be skeptical about their implementation.

Opportunities. The introduction of the proposed approaches will expand the possibilities of both practical activities in the field of state security and public administration of state security, and in the field of educational and scientific directions 251 «State security» and 281 «Public administration and administration». In the context of global trends and processes, the implementation of the author's approaches will allow balancing the attention of scientists and practitioners between all the proposed elements of state security.

Threats. The threat of the spread of the proposed concept of state security and its structuring is the insufficient level of training of specialists (both those who carry out such activities in practice and those who train specialists in these areas) in relation to other socio-economic areas. Changing curricula and training programs will also take a certain amount of time and will not contribute to the overall development of both state security and its management.

8. Conclusions

1. For the development of substantive components of «state security», the analysis of interpretations of «state security» was carried out and the author's definition was formed. It is proposed to understand the state of protection of different-vector interests of the state and the citizen, in which the effective functioning of all spheres, industries, institutional sectors, mechanisms, the implementation of the functions and powers of the state with the aim of their development is ensured. An important emphasis on this state is seen in its achievement in a changing environment, external and internal threats.

2. The components of state security have been determined and their substantive characteristics have been provided. On the basis of a critical analysis of approaches to the components of state security, taking into account the development trends of modern society (globalization processes, sustainable development goals, the transition of mankind to the phase of the information society and the sixth technological order, etc.), the elemental composition of state security is proposed. It includes: the security of general government; political security; economic security; military security; security of public and legal order; social and humanitarian security; information and communication

security; resource and environmental safety; technical and technological safety; international diplomatic security.

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